

Original Research Article

Political Violence in Regional Cinematic Expression: Critical Analysis of a Select Bengali Film

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ABSTRACT

Political violence encompasses a diverse range of actions aimed at causing physical, psychological, and symbolic harm to people and property to persuade different audiences to support or oppose certain social, political and cultural change. In such violence, women, minorities or marginalised communities are often at the receiving end whose lives are jeopardised due to death, injuries and damages to properties. Taking the Bengali film *Dharmajuddha* (2022), as a case study, this paper conducts a narrative analysis to flag the discursive use of political and ethnic violence in regional filmic text. The dominant tropes used in this film through omission, trivialisation and condemnation revolve around the portrayal of people belonging to the margins who become the primary victims of political and ethnic violence.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received on

27 May 2026

Accepted on

30 June 2026

Published on

30 June 2026

KEYWORDS

Bengali Film, Discourse, India,
Marginalised, Political Violence

Vol. 01, No. 01, pp. 57-66

REPRESENT URL

<https://represent.co.in/index.php/rep/article/view/1.1.4>

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21081653>

Introduction

Films act as mirror of society, often influencing the discursive practices in the social life. Kellner (2013) argues that film makers employ visual and narrative tropes related to important historical or contemporary socio-political events and occurrences to appeal to the larger masses, often influenced by their political ideologies or larger narrative. Popular imaginations are fuelled by the images and depictions in mainstream cinema, sometimes fanning fear and prejudice against the represented characters or communities (Hall, 1989). Further, repetitive representation of a skewed version of reality runs the risk of influencing and reinforcing the dominant discourse among the audience (Lippmann, 1922; Hall, 1989).

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The trend of communalization in domestic polity took deep root even though India declared itself a secular nation in spirit (Brass, 2005; Chantler et al., 2019). Despite the secular constitution that India adopted after independence, communal riots and extensive violence against Muslims occurred in the newly established Indian State at the same time, leaving the Muslim population feeling insecure and as second-class citizen (Deshmukh, 2021; Reyaz, 2019). The problems of modernisation and democracy, as well as the potential consequences for women's rights, are reflected in the rise of religious fundamentalism in India (Razavi & Jenichen, 2010).

Women, their bodies in particular, become battlefields in the wake of communal riots, and this was most prominent during the partition-riots that have been immortalised in literature, from Khushwant Singh's *Train to Pakistan* (1956) to Salman Rushdie's *Midnight's Children* (1980), and films like *Chhalia* (1960), *Dharmputra* (1961), *Garm Hawa* (1973), *Tamas* (1988), *Train to Pakistan* (1998), and films like *Mr. and Mrs. Iyer* (2002), *Bishorjan* (2017). Furthermore, Muslims face systemic prejudice that results in their marginalisation in the social, educational, and economic spheres (Kattiparambil, 2023; Fazal, 2024).

Besides communal riots, many Indian states also witnessed political violence perpetuated by foot-soldiers of the political parties owing to the partisan objective of seizing political power and imposing total political hegemony over rivals (Roy, 2024). Most of the violence in states like Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Rajasthan, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, or Maharashtra is caused by conflicts that have their roots in socio-cultural biases and sectarian emotions (Pandey, 1992; Brass, 20025; Kausar, 2006; Kattiparambil, 2023; Fazal, 2024). In West Bengal, meanwhile, political dominance in the use of violence has primarily overshadowed socio-cultural, ideological, and economic considerations where party-society has taken deep roots (Bradbury, 2019; Nath & Ray, 2022). Party loyalty-enmity rhetoric is the driving force behind political violence which makes Bengal apart from other states (Ghosh & Sahoo, 2022, March 28). However, since 2013- 2014 the state has witnessed a spate of communal riots (Reyaz, 2017).

Using narrative analysis of a recently released Bengali film *Dharmajuddha* (2022), co-written and directed by a popular Bengali filmmaker Raj Chakraborty, this paper foregrounds the representation of the communal-political violence that is shaping up the new turn in the state politics and consequent disruptions of the marginalised.

Representation of ethnicity and conflicts in cinema

The portrayal of riots in films is a complex and multi-layered subject that has been explored in numerous academic studies and cinematic traditions. Riots are a form of collective political

violence that often serve as a backdrop for discussing issues such as racial tensions, socioeconomic injustice, and the mechanisms of power and control (Yadav & Singh, 2024). Films by Anurag Kashyap, for instance, are popular for their depictions of political violence in Indian metropolises and their gritty urban realism (Yadav & Singh, 2024).

With increasing diversity among filmmakers and the changing social and political landscape, later films have begun to criticise police racism and brutality, whereas earlier films tended to portray L.A.P.D. personnel as paragons of virtue (Bevan, 2011). Park and Kim (2013) argue that representation of riots often originate from deep-rooted social and economic injustices that are exacerbated by specific historical events. The portrayal of riots in films often centres on racial and ethnic conflict.

Muslims in general are not very influential in public spaces in Bengal despite comprising more than a quarter of the state's population. Muslim identity is individualised in Bengali cinema by portraying Muslims shattered social lives. As a result, Bengali Muslim identity is frequently perceived as being divided along a fault line, with Bengaliness and Muslim identities tensely coexisting on opposing sides of a significant breach. The predominant Bengali vs. Muslim dichotomy can be roughly translated into a set of binary opposites that characterise Bengali Muslim culture (Chatterji, 1996). The women in this place are increasingly oppressed by the male led religious discourses of the society, which keeps them from engaging in any communal discourse (Roohi, 2010).

Muslim characters have, however, made a comeback in Bengali films, in the last decade after a lull in films like *Kabir* (2018), *Zulfiqar* (2016), and *Arshinagar* (2015), etc. But often, they are represented stereotypically where 'Muslims remain the 'other,' in the otherwise land of Durga and Tagore even though a large number of Muslims of Bengal are natives who converted centuries ago (Reyaz, 2016). Members of the Muslim community are portrayed as being oppressed by an orthodox and patriarchal society, where male characters are typically depicted as terrorists or villains in these Bengali movies, and female needing emancipation from their male counterparts (Reyaz, 2016; Khatun 2022).

Theoretical Framework

Building upon the Representation theory of Stuart Hall, this paper foregrounds how cinematic discourse has been used to stereotype the negotiations and marginalization of the victims of communal and political conflicts. Stuart Hall (1997, p. 257) notes that, "Stereotyping reduces people to a few, simple, essential characteristics, which are represented as fixed by Nature. Here, we examine four further aspects: (a) the construction of 'otherness' and exclusion; (b)

stereotyping and power; (c) the role of fantasy; and (d) fetishism". Hall (1997, p.258) further, notes that stereotypes reduce a person to a few "simple, vivid, memorable, easily grasped and widely recognized characteristic" to essentialize, naturalize and fix any deviant differences. This symbolic difference between the "normal" and the "deviant" binds the normal-us and excludes the deviant-others to exercise power over the excluded group. This paper, hence borrows the concept of stereotyping and symbolic representation of power over the marginalised in the analysis of as the excluded group through their vilification through narrative filmic text by demonising them for the communal and political conflicts. The concept of "gross inequalities of power" may be applied to understand the deprivations, angst and frustrations of the marginalised groups over political and governance erupt into distrust and enmity between various religious or ethnic groups (Hall, 1997, p.258). We also borrow the concept of "symbolic power" and "ritualized expulsion" of Stuart Hall (1997, p.259) to understand how the represented groups are identified in the conflict. Stuart Hall (1997, p.259) defines symbolic power as opposed to power that is more direct and coercion but symbolic power as "power to mark, assign and classify...broader cultural or symbolic terms, including the power to represent someone or something in a certain way - within a certain 'regime of representation'. It includes the exercise of symbolic power through representational practices."

Methodology

This article examines the portrayals of Muslim characters in Indian Bengali political violence films through narrative analysis. Narrative analysis interprets texts or visual data and examines the stories' content, structure, and goals. It thus focuses on the context of the narrative to connect the visual elements words and images with a cohesive plot. Marie Gillespie (2006, p. 83) states that narrative analysis of media text helps us to understand "how media narratives work" and explain "the causes and effects of events and actions" consequently "how media construct our knowledge of the world". Further, narrative analysis help us gain "insight into operations of power", "told from particular perspectives, privileging certain viewpoints and versions of events over others" (Gillespie, 2006, p.83). Hence, some stories about conflict, environmental issues or marginalisation are intentionally "produced and circulated by large multinational media corporations, can achieve unprecedented levels of exposure, prominence and power, such that they seem to be the only version of a story to tell" (Gillespie, 2006, p. 83). Further, Gillespie (2006, p. 91) notes that "a narrative is a sequence of events that are linked causally in time and space" and distinguishes the difference between the plot and story. Narrative analysis looks at the plot as something that the storytellers intend and story is something that the audience receive to make sense of the narrative (Gillespie, 2006, p. 91). Taking the three dimensions of narrative as causality, time and space, we study a select film to

understand how such films of political violence construct our knowledge of the predicaments of the marginalised and vulnerable sections during such crisis.

Among approximately 177 films released between January 2021 and December 2023, only ten of them had Muslim protagonists either in leading or supporting roles, out of which two films was based in the context of political violence in West Bengal in India: Raj Chakraborty's *Dharmajuddha* (2022), Arindum Bhattacharjee's *Shibpur* (2023). This study focuses on the film *Dharmajuddha* (Chakraborty, 2022) as a case study due to the prominent roles of marginalised and oppressed sections of society, including Muslims, women and working class as protagonists in the film. Borrowing from the methodology of Gillespie (2006, p.91), we watched the film multiple times to soak ourselves in its narrative structure and then reflect on the various characters and their particular traits such as "attitudes, beliefs, values, tastes, appearances, psychological dispositions, past experiences" as they act as "the main agents of change" in the film narrative. The delineation of the cause-effect chain in the plot of the film *Dharmajuddha* (Chakraborty, 2022) help us identify various stereotypical representational tropes exploited by the filmmaker to tell the story of the marginalized and vulnerable sections who are most affected during any conflict. We study the characters sequentially as they appear in the narrative, generating a coherent story, delineating the introduction, predicaments, conflicts, and resolution.

Narrative Analysis of the film *Dharmajuddha*

The main plot of *Dharmajuddha* revolves around a communal riot in small fictional town Ismailpur. As the riots break out, forced by the situations, four victims who are otherwise rivals to each other take shelter at an old woman's house, Ammi/Amma (played by Swatilekha Sengupta). They are Munni (played by Subhashree Ganguly), Jabbar (played by Soham Chakraborty), Raghav (played by Ritwick Chakraborty), and Shabnam (played by Parno Mitra). As the story unfolds, we get to know how each of them faced the riots and the roles they played.

The film begins with an old frail lady worried to catch up the news in a dimly lit old house, due to power cut, amidst communal tensions in the area established in an earlier shot with a torched vehicle. The old lady is shown sheltering four people who all enquire her religious identity on first encounter, but never clearly reveal it to let them reason to stay on the grounds of humanity rather than religious affiliation. She is equally sensitive to Shabnam, a Muslim girl, and Munni, a pregnant Hindu lady amidst her deep concern for her son's absence offering food, pacifying, these refugees from warring among themselves. When Raghav asked Munni about her religion, Ammi replied to him, '*Yeh Hindu yeh Musulman yeh sab mare pet se hi hai* [She is Hindu, and

she is Muslim, all of them are my children] (Chakraborty, 2022, 00:54:33). When the four refugees in her house start quarrelling among themselves, she insists: '*Iss ghar mein wahi rahega jo dharm se upar insan ko manta hai* [Only those can live in this house who consider humanity above religion]' (Chakraborty, 2022, 00:55:29). Her house thus becomes a metaphor for India where she urges all citizens to let go of their fear and grudges and learn to live peacefully together. She quivers, '*Kuchh iss tarah maine zindagi ko asann karliya, kisi se mafi mang lii, kisi ko maaf kardiyaa* [In such a way, I made life a little easier, sought for forgiveness from some, forgave some others]' (Chakraborty, 2022, 00:33:07).

Munni narrates how her husband, Ratan, an auto driver, was used as a pawn to instigate the communal tension in the locality. She states how Ratan, threatened to lose his road permit, had to hoist a saffron flag atop a local mosque at the behest of the rightwing leader to intentionally flare up communal tension in the locality prior to an upcoming election.

Another character in the film, Jabbar had grudges that he was labelled as a Pakistani and beaten by members of a local right-wing party by falsely accusing him of selling beef. Further, the fourth character Raghav, who seeks refuge at the home of the old lady, describes how his Muslim neighbours did not let him practice his religious ritual of blowing conch shell at sunset coinciding with azan (call for prayer in Islam); and neither the police nor local politicians were of any help. In protest he played conch shell on the loudspeaker during the azan angering the Muslim mob that attacked his home. Although he survived, his mother was killed which led him to join the local right-wing forces to take revenge from the perpetrators.

When the violence calmed down in the morning, local police came to Ammi's house to inform her that her son was killed by the mob in the riots at night. Jabbar realises that he was the killer of Ammi's son when the grieving mother takes out the photograph of her deceased son.

Films as a canvas for omission

Films play an important role in shaping and manipulating the ideas and narratives around a subject. After 2014, several communal riots occurred in Bengal in places like Uttar Dinajpur, Howrah, Canning, Basirhat, Barrackpore, Deganga, Malda, etc. This article thus foregrounds the broader connection between the socio-political setting and how Muslims are portrayed in Bengali films. The portrayal of Muslims in Bengali films thus changes in response to the contemporary political climate. Muslims are often expected to forsake their religious identities for them to be more acceptable by the larger society.

On the surface, the film *Dharmajuddha*, appears to have been made with well intentions, and covering a very critical issue of the politics behind communal riots. But it suffers from the

typical stereotypical tropes. The filmmaker tries to keep suspense on whether the old lady is a Muslim or Hindu, presenting her more as a symbol of secular nation. From the starting montage to the overall portrayal of Muslims appear very problematic. Except Shabnam, there is hardly any Muslim who is well behaved in this film. In a way the real culprits for the tragedy in her life are not the Hindus who attacked her house, but the conservative Muslims who could not tolerate her relationships with a Hindu man.

Even if Jabbar is shown as a victim of the circumstances, he is the murderer of the son of the old lady who gave him refuge and thus must live with this remorse. Meanwhile, Raghav is a victim of the so called ‘pseudo secular’ politics of ‘appeasement’ of Muslims who did not have the freedom to practice his religion as he was living in a locality surrounded by Muslims. While such narratives about communal riots in India are not new, particularly in media, where fundamentalists and politically motivated groups on both sides are blamed for fomenting riots to reap political benefits, all serious scholarships on riots show that Muslims are often at the receiving ends of riots (Bohlken & Sergenti, 2010; Wilkinson, 2009), and that the fringe groups often have the support of the ‘institutionalized riot systems’ (Brass 2005).

Dominant tropes of trivialisation and condemnation

The way, the film was peppered with some dialogues in Urdu/Hindustani in an otherwise Bengali-language film, especially when the conversation of Jabbar comes, or in the context of Muslims narration is also problematic. In fact, a Muslim cleric is shown as giving provocative speech in Urdu using words like kafir (infidels), jihad against Hindus, and that the martyrs will go straight to the paradise are not only stereotypical, but end up vilifying and otherising Muslims, men in particular, while Muslim woman (Shabnam) is shown as the one that needs saving from the fundamentalists and patriarchal Muslim men.

Often these films predate on the memories and trauma of the past conflicts ingrained or fanned by different political regimes, in popular imaginations. These films monetise on the fear and divisive discourses of other media narratives and political discourse of contemporary times to trivialise issues around death and despair post conflict.

Biased portrayal of the margins

The film may appear outrightly preachy in the character of Ammi as an allegory of Mother India, but it also succeeds in churning our stomach with the scenes of death and despair that occurs around the lives of women, who are not individuals but are identified as mothers, wives, daughters, lovers and sisters. In one scene, Ammi reiterates: ‘*Main woh sab kuchh hun jisme sab ki bhalai ho* (I am all those that can be in the interest of everyone)’ (Chakraborty, 2022,

00:49:45). While the film may have tried to lamb the women who need saving from men, by men, throughout the filmic narrative, however it consciously demonises the men by painting them as perpetrators. The passing reference to the lived experiences of poor marginalised, daily earning male, often victimised by red-tapism, and political nexus appears as a lip service in the film to give portrayal to the margins.

Conclusion

Conflicts often result in gender-based violence, which the film foregrounds with the birth of the girl child, hinting that she too may end up facing the same, at one point in her life. It also points towards the political exploitation of the vulnerabilities in flaring up communal conflicts. These structural discourses in popular culture feed on the inherent biases about the marginalised and oppressed, including Muslims, women and working class, both among the general audiences and the film makers. They weave in the usual barbaric, rustic, intolerant, hostile representational tropes for the marginalised to reinforce their otherisation in popular memory and imaginations. We hence, locate the nuances of filmic discourses used in such films to show how political and ethnic violence disrupt lives of the marginalised irrespective of their religious affiliations. Lives at the margins are crumpled and displaced due to conflicts. This film do not stop at only giving space to displacement and conflict but also shows the scope for reconciliation post conflict for the marginalised and led by the marginalised. The conflict in this film does not simply serve the purpose of driving the plot but also present nuances of the multiple interpersonal and socio-political disagreements between the citizens of a nation, especially the working class. In this film the women are used as the metaphor of all embracing and sacrificing mother nature, while questioning the dependency of their existence and identity with respect to their male counterparts, either husband, son or lover. The death of each of these male members of their family pushes them into deeper agony at the thought of insecurity and uncertainty of approaching future. The external conflict with the other community doubled their internal conflicts of negotiating their own conscience post self-realisation of the loss and despair in the other community caused by their fellow community members. The film also reiterates the saying of an eye of an eye makes the world blind and signifies the loss of life and livelihood during the end credits roll of the film with data and actual images of refugee camps in India at different places post several religious conflicts at different times in the past few decades.

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